

РАЗДЕЛ. МЕДИЦИНСКИЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4782048>

УДК 614.1

**АНАЛИЗ ДИНАМИКИ И ПРИЧИН СМЕРТНОСТИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ
НЕКОТОРЫХ РЕГИОНОВ РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ
В ПОСТЧЕРНОБЫЛЬСКИЙ ПЕРИОД**

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Аннотация: В работе проведен сравнительный анализ динамики смертности населения некоторых областей Республики Беларусь в постчернобыльский период в сравнении с общереспубликанскими показателями. В результате проведенного исследования установлен рост показателя общей смертности в целом по стране на 27,7 % (с 1100,1 в 1990 г. до 1520,0 на 100 тыс. в 2018 г.), его максимум приходился на 2005 и 2010 года и составлял 1450,5 и 1444,9 соответственно. Наибольший коэффициент общей смертности в Гомельской и Витебской областях был зарегистрирован в 2002 году (1560,0 и 1680,0 соответственно), в Гродненской области в 2005 году (1620,0). Наивысший коэффициент общей смертности населения в Витебской и Гродненской областях был зарегистрирован в 2005 году (876,6 и 891,1), в Гомельской в 2010 году (849,0). На втором месте среди причин смертности находятся злокачественные образования.

Ключевые слова: смертность населения, общая смертность, коэффициент общей смертности, постчернобыльский период

**THE ANALYSIS OF DYNAMICS AND THE REASONS OF
MORTALITY OF THE POPULATION OF SOME REGIONS OF
REPUBLIC OF BELARUS DURING THE POST-CHERNOBYL
PERIOD**

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Annotation: In work the comparative analysis of dynamics of mortality of the population of some areas of Republic of Belarus is carried out to the post-Chernobyl period in comparison with all-republican indicators. As a result of the conducted research growth of an indicator of the general mortality countrywide by 27.7 % is established (from 1100.1 in 1990 up to 1520.0 on 100 thousand in 2018), its maximum fell on 2005 and 2010 and made 1450.5 and 1444.9 respectively. The greatest coefficient of the general mortality in the Gomel and Vitebsk regions was registered in 2002 (1560.0 and 1680.0 respectively), in the Grodno region in 2005 (1620.0). The highest coefficient of the general mortality of the population in the Vitebsk and Grodno regions was registered in 2005 (876.6 and 891.1), in Gomel in 2010 (849.0). Malignancies are in the second place among the reasons of mortality.

Keywords: population mortality, general mortality, coefficient of the general mortality, post-Chernobyl period

Relevance. Harmful and dangerous factors of the environment create threat for health and life of the population. In the conditions of ecologically destabilized environment, the level of health decreases and life expectancy of the person is reduced. In this, regard important and relevant to analyze dynamics and structure of mortality. The comparative analysis and studying of rates of mortality of the population of the Gomel, Grodno and Vitebsk regions as regions with the different level of radiocontamination in connection with the Chernobyl accident, which considerably affected an ecological situation in Republic of Belarus, and the social and psychological status of the population is of interest [1-8].

Purpose. The comparative analysis of dynamics of mortality of the population of the Republic of Belarus some areas during the post-Chernobyl period in comparison with all-republican indicators.

Materials and methods of a research. In work it is used comparative and estimated and analytical methods for studying of official statistical data of the Ministry of Health of Republic of Belarus.

Results and discussion. From 1985 for 2000 the coefficient of the general mortality on 100 thousand population changed as follows: in the Gomel region: 1985 – 1023.2; 1990 – 1090.0; 1995 – 1360.0; 2000 – 1400.5; in the Vitebsk region: 1985 – 1230.0; 1990 – 1250; 1995 – 1490.0; 2000 – 1510.5; in the Grodno region: 1985 – 1193.6; 1990 – 1150.0; 1995 – 1370.0; 2000 – 1416.5; across Republic of Belarus: 1985 – 1057.0; 1990 – 1100.2; 1995 – 1350.1; 2000 – 1520.0. Thus, from 1985 for 2000 the coefficient of the general mortality in the Gomel region increased from 10.2 to 14.0, or for 37.1%, in Vitebsk – from 12.3 to 15.1 or for 18.6 %, in Grodno – from 11.9 to 14.2 or for 15.8 %, across Republic of Belarus – from 10.6 to 15.2 or for 31 %. The mortality rate in the polluted territories of the Gomel region (10 administrative regions) as in to – and post-Chernobyl period exceeded average regional and national average values. In addition, it should be noted, as its gain for 1985-2000 was the greatest. From 1990 for 2000 the coefficient of the general mortality from infectious and parasitic diseases in the Gomel region increased from 7.3 to 10.8 or by 48 %, in the Vitebsk region – from 7.0 to 10.1 or for 43 %, in the Grodno region – from 6 to 8.9 or for 46 %, across Republic of Belarus – from 7.1 to 9.5 or for 21 %. The coefficient of the general mortality from malignant new growths in the Gomel region increased from 166.3 to 194.8 or by 17 %, in the Vitebsk region – from 207.0 to 214.5 or for 5 %, in the Grodno region – from 170.6 to 206.5 or for 21 %, across Republic of Belarus – from 173.5 to 196.1 or for 14 %. Coefficient of the general mortality from blood circulatory system diseases in the Gomel region – with 635.8 to 785.7 or for 23 %, in the Vitebsk region – with 570.6 to 823.1 or for 46 %, in the Grodno region – with 543.3 to 749.6 or for 38 %, across Republic of Belarus – with 547.0 to 725.5 or for 34 %.

As before accident mortality city and villagers authentically differed, influence of a radiation factor on its dynamics has to be considered separately for these categories of the population. During the post-Chernobyl period from 1985 to 2000, the mortality rate both at city, and at rural the population considerably increased. In the Gomel region increased (urban population from 6.9 to 10.6, country people from 15.1 to 21.6); The Grodno region (urban population with 6.9 to 9.1, country people with 17.4 to 22.9); The Vitebsk region (urban population with 8.4 to 11.5, country people with 18.5 to 22.7).

From 2000 for 2018 the coefficient of the general mortality changed as follows: in the Gomel region: 2000 – 1400.5; 2005 – 1510.0; 2010 – 1510.7; 2015 – 1380.0; 2018-1310.0; in the Vitebsk region: 2000 – 1510.5; 2005 – 1650.3; 2010 – 1670.2; 2015 – 1470.8; 2018-1460.0; in the Grodno region: 2000 – 1420.5; 2005 – 1620.2; 2010 – 1560.0; 2015 – 1380.0; 2018-1400.0;

Across Republic of Belarus: 2000 – 1520.0; 2005 – 1550.5; 2010 – 1420.0; 2015 – 1280.0; 2018-1250.0. Thus, from 2000 for 2018 the coefficient of the general mortality in the Gomel region decreased from 14.0 to 13.1 %, in Grodno – from 14.2 to 14.0 %, across Republic of Belarus – from 15.2 to 12.5 %, in Vitebsk from 15.1 to 14.6 %.

From 2005 for 2018 the mortality rate among urban population of the Vitebsk region decreased from 1270.2 to 1200.6 or for 5.5 %; in the Grodno region – with 1060.6 to 970.4 or for 8.5 %; in the Gomel region with 1151.5 to 1070.8 or for 7 %.

From 2000 for 2018 the coefficient of the general mortality from infectious and parasitic diseases in the Gomel region increased from 10.8 to 15.3 or by 41.7 %; in the Vitebsk region decreased from 10.1 to 5.2 or for 4.9 %; in the Grodno region – with 8.9 to 6.0 or for 32.6 %; across Republic of Belarus – with 9.5 to 7.3 or for 23.2 %. The coefficient of the general mortality from malignant new growths in the Gomel region increased from 194.8 to 218.9 or by 12.4 %; in the Vitebsk region – with 214.5 to 223.8 or for 4.3 %; in the Grodno region went down from 206.5 to 179.2 or for 13.2 %; across Republic of Belarus – with 196.1 to 198.7 or for 1.3 %. The coefficient of the general mortality from blood circulatory system diseases in the Gomel region decreased from 785.8 to 774.4 or for 1.5 %; in the Vitebsk region – with 823.1 to 709.0 or for 13.9 %; in the Grodno region increased from 749.6 to 804.0 or by 7.3 %; across Republic of Belarus decreased from 725.5 to 718.0 or for 1 %.

The maximum quantity of diseases of the blood circulatory system in structure of the reasons of mortality from all considered regions falls on the period from 2000 to 2010. Most often in a class of diseases of the blood circulatory system coronary heart disease, acute cerebrovascular diseases mortality without hypertension, other forms of heart troubles was registered.

The following disease in structure of the reasons of mortality of the population are new growths to which share more than 99 % fall. Are common causes of death at men a carcinoma cutaneum, a stomach, a rectum, a prostate gland, lymphatic and haematogenic fabrics; women have malignant new growths of a mammary gland, a tumor of lungs, a stomach, ovaries, colonic and a rectum, necks of uterus, lymphatic and haematogenic fabrics.

Conclusions. As a result of the analysis of dynamics of mortality of the population growth of an indicator of the general mortality countrywide by 27.7 % is established (from 1100.1 in 1990 up to 1520.0 on 100 thousand in 2018), and its maximum fell on 2005 and 2010 and made 1450.5 and 1444.9 respectively. The greatest coefficient of the general mortality in the Gomel and

Vitebsk regions was registered in 2002 (1560.0 and 1680.0 respectively), in the Grodno region in 2005 (1620.0). Among the population mortality reasons blood circulatory system diseases are in the first place. The highest coefficient of the general mortality of the population in the Vitebsk and Grodno regions was registered in 2005 (876.6 and 891.1), in Gomel in 2010 (849.0). Malignancies are in the second place among the reasons of mortality. The highest coefficient of the general mortality on Vitebsk and Gomel areas was registered in 2018 (223.8 and 218.9), in the Grodno region in 2000 (206.5).

In general, the analysis of official statistical data allows drawing conclusions that, despite decrease in total area of pollution, indicators of primary incidence and the general mortality of the population increase. Mortality of the population of the Gomel region remains rather high and exceeds regional average values over the country.

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Поступила в редакцию 10.04.2021

Принята к публикации 15.04.2021

Для цитирования:

Александрович А.С., Зиматкина Т.И. Анализ динамики и причин смертности населения некоторых регионов республики Беларусь в постчернобыльский период // Инновационные научные исследования : сетевой журнал. 2021. № 4-2(6). С. 145-150. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>